

The David Hide Asthma & Allergy Research Centre

CLINICAL STUDY PROTOCOL

Title: THE EFFECT OF DYSON AIR PURIFIER IN IMPROVING ASTHMA CONTROL - A RANDOMISED, CONTROLLED TRIAL

Short Title: Dyson air purifier in asthma

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Study Synopsis

Title:	THE EFFECT OF DYSON AIR PURIFIER IN IMPROVING ASTHMA CONTROL - A RANDOMISED, CONTROLLED TRIAL
Short Title:	Dyson air purifier in asthma
Sponsor:	Research & Development, Isle of Wight NHS Trust, Isle of Wight
Chief Investigator:	Professor S. Hasan Arshad
REC Reference:	18/WM/0277
Research question:	Does Dyson air purifier, by reducing indoor allergens and pollutants (as specified in 2.1), reduce bronchial hyper-responsiveness and improve poor asthma control in mild to moderate persistent asthmatics?
Primary Objective:	To investigate the effect of reducing the level of allergens and pollutants in the bedroom and living room by placing a “Dyson air purifier”, on poorly controlled asthmatic subjects.
Design:	Randomised, Double Blind, Controlled Trial
Sample Size:	50 (25 in each group)
Inclusion Criteria:	<ol style="list-style-type: none">1. Patients between 18 to 75 years of age with a confirmed diagnosis of mild to moderate persistent asthma (BTS steps “regular preventer therapy” to “additional add-on therapies”).2. Poorly controlled asthma defined by ACQ6 score >1.5
Exclusion Criteria:	<p>Patients with significant chronic respiratory disease such as COPD or bronchiectasis.</p> <p>Patients with any severe disease (such as cardiovascular disease, dementia etc.), where adherence to the study protocol may cause an unjustified stress.</p> <p>Those who are being treated with allergen specific immunotherapy.</p> <p>Patients with a history of significant alcohol or drug abuse.</p> <p>Patients who are taking an investigational drug for asthma.</p> <p>Patients who are unwilling, unlikely or unable to comply with the study protocol.</p> <p>Patients who are likely to be started on biological therapy during the study period.</p> <p>Pregnancy.</p> <p>Patients already using air purifiers in their dwellings.</p> <p>Patients planning to move house within the study period.</p> <p><u>Patients without a WIFI connection in their dwelling.</u></p>
Trial Site:	David Hide Asthma and Allergy Research Centre, Isle of Wight
Protocol Version/ Date:	Version 8.2: 03/10/2018

Contents

1.	BACKGROUND AND RATIONALE.....	5
1.1.	COMPLIANCE STATEMENT.....	6
2.	HYPOTHESIS OBJECTIVE AND OUTCOMES.....	6
2.1.	INTERVENTION TO BE TESTED:.....	6
2.2.	OBJECTIVE:.....	6
2.3.	HYPOTHESIS:	6
2.4.	PRIMARY ENDPOINTS.....	6
2.5.	SECONDARY ENDPOINTS.....	7
3.	SELECTION OF STUDY PARTICIPANTS	7
3.1.	SAMPLE SIZE.....	7
3.2.	INCLUSION CRITERIA	7
3.3.	EXCLUSION CRITERIA.....	7
4.	METHODS.....	8
4.1.	PARTICIPANT SELECTION, ENROLMENT AND CONSENT	8
4.2.	STUDY CENTRE.....	9
4.3.	STUDY DESIGN.....	9
4.4.	VISITS	9
4.5.	SPECIFIC CLINICAL METHODS.....	13
4.5.1.	Questionnaires	13
4.5.2.	Physical Examination	13
4.5.3.	Skin Prick Test.....	13
4.5.4.	Spirometry	13
4.5.5.	Bronchial Hyperresponsiveness.....	14
4.5.6.	Fractional Exhaled Nitric Oxide (FeNO) measurements:	14
4.6.	STUDY DURATION	15
5.	DATA MANAGEMENT	15
5.1.	DATA PROTECTION AND STORAGE	15
5.2.	STATISTICAL METHODS.....	16
6.	ETHICS	16
6.1.	ADVERSE EVENTS.....	16

6.2.	SAFEGUARDING	16
7.	FINANCE AND INSURANCE	16
8.	TRIAL MANAGEMENT AND OVERSIGHT ARRANGEMENTS	17
9.	GOOD CLINICAL PRACTICE	17
10.	STUDY CONDUCT RESPONSIBILITIES	20
11.	REPORTING, PUBLICATIONS AND NOTIFICATION OF RESULTS.....	22
12.	REFERENCES	23

1. BACKGROUND AND RATIONALE

Asthma is one of the most common chronic diseases. Little change in morbidity and mortality has occurred despite improvements in pharmacotherapy. In the last few decades, there has been an increase in the prevalence of asthma and other allergic diseases. The precise cause for this increase in disease prevalence is not known but it has coincided with changes to the quality of indoor air with increases in the levels of allergens and pollutants. Bedroom exposure to dust-mite allergens has been linked to worsening asthma symptoms and increase in bronchial responsiveness.¹ In places where dust mites cannot thrive, allergens from cat, cockroach and *Alternaria* assume importance. High indoor temperatures and humidity may, by a number of mechanisms, increase the allergenic burden, particularly the proliferation of house-dust mites and moulds. Therefore, modern living conditions are associated with a higher risk of allergen exposure causing increase in sensitisation and symptoms of asthma. In addition to allergens, the indoor environment contains other biological materials (such as microbiome and endotoxin), and pollutants (gases and particulate matter) which can adversely affect asthma development and morbidity. Indoor pollutants include smoke from cigarettes and wood, coal or gas fires, particulate materials associated with bio-fuel combustion, chemical vapours and gases including nitrogen dioxide (NO₂), formaldehyde and volatile organic compounds (VOCs). The latter may come from sources including building products, cleaning agents, and paints. One such VOC is formaldehyde, which can be irritant to both upper and lower respiratory tract. Small particulate matter (PM_{2.5}) is particularly damaging as it gets to the small airways of the lung. Major indoor sources of NO₂ and particulate matter include gas stoves and cigarette smoke but outdoor sources such as traffic and industrial pollution can also contaminate indoor environment.²

It has also been suggested that exposure to pollutants can potentiate the effects of allergen.³ Indeed, a combination of high levels of indoor pollution and allergens is causally related to the development and severity of asthma.⁴ Allergens, microbiome and pollutants can interact with each other to augment the immune response leading to harmful effects on the airways.^{5,6}

Thus, indoor air pollution is a significant environmental trigger for acute exacerbation of asthma (and other respiratory conditions such as COPD), leading to increasing symptoms, emergency department visits, hospital admissions and even mortality. An estimated 75% of hospital admissions for asthma are avoidable. Maintaining high air quality with lower levels of allergens and pollutants is therefore important in improving the health of individuals with asthma and other respiratory diseases. Therefore, a feasible and practical intervention that can reduce allergen and pollutant levels in the indoor air should reduce morbidity and improve asthma control.

A workshop was convened recently by the National Institute of Health, USA (Professor Arshad was invited as an expert panel member and co-authored the recommendations) to examine the current status of indoor environment in improving asthma control.⁴ The workshop concluded that apart from replacement of gas stoves with electric stoves, and avoidance of indoor smoking, few methods are currently available for reduction of indoor NO₂ and possibly other pollutants. Allergen

reduction methods have similarly shown conflicting results. Technological improvements have been made in the efficacy of high-efficiency particulate air (HEPA) particle filtration designed to remove targeted indoor air pollutants, such as fine particulate matter (PM_{2.5}).⁷ Some studies have shown a positive effect of using air cleaner with HEPA and carbon filters on asthma symptoms.⁸⁻¹⁰ Although, most studies using air purifiers show reduction in gases and particulate matter, the overall effect on asthma control remains uncertain. Allergen reduction intervention studies have shown similarly inconsistent results (summarised in Table II; Reference 5). Therefore, we need novel intervention strategies that can reduce both allergens and pollutants in the indoor environment to the extent that can improve asthma control and reduce airway inflammation and hyper-responsiveness. Recently, nocturnal temperature controlled laminar airflow technology has been investigated for treating atopic asthma with some effects.¹¹ There is some suggestion that this strategy of reducing indoor exposure to allergens and pollutants might be cost effective.¹² However, the result of a large randomised controlled trial is awaited.

1.1. COMPLIANCE STATEMENT

This trial will be conducted in compliance with this Protocol, GCP and any applicable local or regulatory requirements.

2. HYPOTHESIS OBJECTIVE AND OUTCOMES

2.1. INTERVENTION TO BE TESTED: Dyson Pure Cool™ Tower. Dyson purifying fans sense particulates (PM₁₀, PM_{2.5}) and gases (VOC, NO₂) and capture pollution (HEPA filtration 99.95% PM_{0.1} and Tris impregnated carbon granules to capture gases such as formaldehyde, benzene and nitrogen dioxide), then disperse purified air throughout the whole room through forward projection.

2.2. OBJECTIVE: the primary objective is to investigate the effect of reducing the level of allergens and pollutants in the bedroom and living room on poor asthma control by placing a “Dyson air purifier” with asthmatic subjects. Primary and secondary outcome variables have been selected to evaluate this effect.

2.3. HYPOTHESIS: We hypothesise that Dyson air purifier added to the standard treatment will improve poor asthma control, as assessed by ACQ6 composite score and quality of life, as assessed by AQLQ scores, as a result of reducing allergen and pollutant levels.

2.4. PRIMARY ENDPOINTS

- Change in Juniper asthma specific quality of life (AQLQ) scores: A change in score of 0.5 on the 7-point scale is considered clinically important (Minimal Important Difference).

- Change in asthma control composite scores using Juniper asthma control questionnaire (ACQ6). A change in score of 0.5 on the 6-point scale is considered clinically important.

2.5. SECONDARY ENDPOINTS

- Change in airway responsiveness from baseline will be compared in the two groups (as assessed by methacholine bronchial challenge).
- Changes in indoor levels of pollutants that are recorded by Dyson purifier.
- Pulmonary function as assessed by changes in forced expiratory volume in one second (FEV₁), FEV₁/FVC ratio, and mid expiratory flows.
- Change in exhaled nitric oxide levels (as an indicator of airway inflammation) from baseline will be compared in the two groups.

3. SELECTION OF STUDY PARTICIPANTS

3.1. SAMPLE SIZE

As this is a first of a kind study, estimates of effect size are not available for sample size calculation. However, other studies have shown that a clinical response can be demonstrated using a HEPA filter with as few as 15 patients in each group.¹⁰ Hence, our sample size of 25 in each group is likely to provide an indication of whether Dyson purifier improves asthma control.

3.2. INCLUSION CRITERIA

- Patients between 18 to 75 years of age with a confirmed diagnosis of mild to moderate persistent asthma (BTS steps “regular preventer therapy” to “additional add-on therapies”)
- ACQ6 score >1.5.

3.3. EXCLUSION CRITERIA

- Patients with significant chronic respiratory disease such as COPD or bronchiectasis.
- Patients with any severe disease (such as cardiovascular disease, dementia etc.), where adherence to the study protocol may cause an unjustified stress.
- Those who are being treated with allergen specific immunotherapy.

- Patients with a history of significant alcohol or drug abuse.
- Patients who are taking an investigational drug for asthma.
- Patients who are unwilling, unlikely or unable to comply with the study protocol, as assessed by the study team members.
- Patients who are likely to be started on biological therapies for asthma (omalizumab, mepolizumab, reslizumab, dupilumab) during the study period.
- Pregnancy.
- Patients already using air purifiers in their dwellings.
- Patients planning to move house during the study period.

4. METHODS

4.1. PARTICIPANT SELECTION, ENROLMENT AND CONSENT

- We aim to recruit 50 mild persistent to moderately severe asthma (BTS steps “regular preventer therapy” to “additional add-on therapies”) subjects from our asthma outpatient clinics and primary care health centres, with 1:1 randomisation (n=25 in each group). Ethics approval will be sought from National Research Ethics Committees. The written informed consent will be obtained from all subjects and a confidentiality agreement will be signed. Asthmatics in both groups will be told that the effect of Dyson air purifier is being tested and that they will have an equal chance of being randomised to an active or placebo filter purifier. Both, the active and the placebo purifier will be installed in the house for 6 months. Both, the participants, Chief and Co-Investigators (henceforth referred to as “Investigators”) and the study team members (Research fellow, Nurses, CTAs and Study Co-ordinators) will remain blind to the group allocation.
- Both study group participants will be assessed at baseline. Dyson air purifier (with active or placebo filter) will be installed in the bedroom and living room of the house following randomisation for a period of 6 months (a minimum of 6 months period of intervention will be required). Patients will be monitored throughout this period, as detailed below (Table1). The purifiers and filters will be provided by Dyson and the changing of the filters will be carried out by a Clinical Trial Assistant based at the David Hide Asthma and Allergy Research Centre (DHAARC). The subject’s General Practitioner will be informed. We estimate that the overall RCT duration will be 12 months (see study schedule), including recruitment and assessments.

- After the 6 months period of intervention, all the data will be collected and analysed for the main study (RCT). However, we propose to have an extension of 6 months as an open phase to follow where all patients will be offered an active purifier filter (for both original placebo and active group patients). All these patients will complete (ACQ and AQLQ) questionnaires at 3 months and have a full assessment at the end of this second phase.

4.2. STUDY CENTRE

The DHAARC (www.allergyresearch.org.uk) is situated at the site of St. Mary's Hospital on the Isle of Wight. It has been established as a Centre of excellence over the last 22 years. It provides NHS asthma and allergy services for the Island. It is closely associated with the University of Southampton and conducts clinical studies in asthma and allergy. The Centre has access to asthma patients through its outpatient clinics as well as through its close working relationship with the Island GPs. Asthma study patients will be recruited through clinic database and through primary care in close cooperation with GPs and asthma practice nurses. The clinical aspects of the study will be based at this Centre.

4.3. STUDY DESIGN

This is a randomised, double blind, placebo (filter) controlled trial.

4.4. VISITS

All procedures will be performed by a member of the study team (Research Fellow, Nurses and CTAs) working closely with the Investigators.

Centre Visit 1 (Screening/baseline visit)

- The nature and duration of the study will be explained and informed consent will be obtained.
- Global Evaluation of Asthma using Asthma Control Questionnaire (ACQ6) will be carried out.
- A brief medical history and physical examination will be performed to assess their suitability for the study, including demography, vital signs, allergic history and asthma medication, using standardised questionnaires.
- A questionnaire will be completed to assess environmental exposures including the presence of pets, smoking and gas stove in the house.
- A recording of which machine is in which room is to be made (living room & Bedroom).

- Asthma related quality of life assessment using self-administered Juniper Mini asthma quality of life questionnaire (AQLQ).
- Rhinitis related quality of life assessment using self-administered Juniper Rhinitis quality of life questionnaire (RQLQ).
- Allergy skin prick test to assess their allergy to common aeroallergens.
- Lung function test (Spirometry).
- Methacholine bronchial challenge test to assess bronchial hyper-responsiveness.
- Exhaled nitric oxide measurement using NIOX MINO to assess airway inflammation.
- All subjects will be invited to provide a 20ml blood sample for immunological analysis.
- Asthma diary capturing symptoms, medications, any exacerbations and record of peak flow will be provided for completion at home over the next 2 weeks.
- A standard letter will be sent to the GP if the patient is enrolled on to the study

Home Visit 1 (2-4 weeks after screening visit 1):

A Clinical Trial Assistant (CTA) will visit the house to install Dyson purifier in the intervention group (active) and control group (placebo). Asthma diary including peak flow readings will have been completed/recorded for baseline symptoms assessment for at least 2 weeks and this will be collected. The participant will also be supplied with an asthma diary to complete over the 2 weeks before the next telephone interview in 6-7 weeks and for 2 weeks prior to the Centre visit in 3 months. Dust samples will be collected from mattress and carpets in bedroom and living room. Measurements of the rooms where the purifiers will be placed will be taken to ensure optimal placement of devices. Check on both devices (bedroom and living room) that the security labels placed on the filters' locking mechanisms are still intact and keep a record.

Interim (telephone contact) at 6 week intervals after each home visit (total 3; at 6-7 weeks, 18-19 weeks and 36-38 weeks): Following procedures will be performed:

- Asthma Control Questionnaire (ACQ), Asthma Quality of Life Questionnaire (AQLQ) and Rhinitis Quality of Life Questionnaire (RQLQ) will be completed/recorded.
- Ensure that asthma diary capturing symptoms, medications, any exacerbations and record of peak flow over the previous 2 weeks has been completed.

Participants will be asked to send back the questionnaires and asthma diary by post in stamped, addressed envelope provided at the screening visit.

Centre Visit 2 (3 months after home visit 1): Following procedures will be performed:

- A brief history, medication usage and physical examination
- Global Evaluation of Asthma using Asthma Control Questionnaire (ACQ) will be carried out.
- Asthma related quality of life assessment using self-administered Junipers mini asthma quality of life questionnaire (AQLQ).
- Rhinitis related quality of life assessment using self-administered Juniper Rhinitis quality of life questionnaire (RQLQ).
- Lung function test (Spirometry).
- Methacholine bronchial challenge test to assess bronchial hyper-responsiveness.
- Exhaled nitric oxide measurement using NIOX MINO to assess airway inflammation.
- Asthma diary capturing symptoms, medications, any exacerbations and record of peak flow over the previous 2 weeks will be collected and a further asthma diary will be issued with instruction to complete this for 2 weeks before the next telephone interview in 6-7 weeks and for 2 weeks prior to the Centre visit in 6 months

Centre Visit 3 (6 months after home visit 1): Following procedures will be performed:

- A brief history, medication usage and physical examination.
- Global Evaluation of Asthma using Asthma Control Questionnaire (ACQ) will be carried out.
- Asthma related quality of life assessment using self-administered Mini Junipers asthma quality of life questionnaire (AQLQ).
- Rhinitis related quality of life assessment using self-administered Juniper Rhinitis quality of life questionnaire (RQLQ).
- Lung function test (Spirometry).
- Methacholine bronchial challenge test to assess bronchial hyper-responsiveness.
- Exhaled nitric oxide measurement using NIOX MINO to assess airway inflammation.

- All subjects will be invited to provide a 20ml blood sample for immunological analysis.
- Asthma diary capturing symptoms, medications, any exacerbations and record of peak flow over the previous 2 weeks will be collected and a further asthma diary will be issued with instructions to complete this for two weeks prior to telephone interview in 3 months and for 2 weeks before end of trial in 6 months.

At the end of the Randomised controlled phase of the trial, all patients, who agreed to participate in the open extension phase for 6 months, will be offered installation of the active filter in their machines (if they were in the placebo group).

Home Visit 2 (End of RCT): A Clinical Trial Assistant (CTA) will visit the house to install active filters for all participants and collect dust samples. Prior to changing the filters check on both devices (bedroom and living room) that the security labels placed on the filters' locking mechanisms are still intact and keep a record. Discarded filters to be sealed in a bag and labelled with participant identification number for potential further analysis. HEPA and Activated Carbon filters to be stored in two different bags.

Centre Visit 4 (12 months after home visit 1): Following procedures will be performed:

- A brief history, medication usage and physical examination.
- Global Evaluation of Asthma using Asthma Control Questionnaire (ACQ) will be carried out.
- Asthma related quality of life assessment using self-administered Mini Junipers asthma quality of life questionnaire (AQLQ).
- Rhinitis related quality of life assessment using self-administered Juniper Rhinitis quality of life questionnaire (RQLQ).
- Lung function test (Spirometry).
- Methacholine bronchial challenge test to assess bronchial hyper-responsiveness.
- Exhaled nitric oxide measurement using NIOX MINO to assess airway inflammation.
- All subjects will be invited to provide a 20ml blood sample for immunological analysis.
- Asthma diary will be collected with two 2 weeks record of symptoms, medication use and peak flows recorded as outline above.

Home Visit 3 (End of study): A Clinical Trial Assistant (CTA) will visit the house to remove air purifiers for return to Dyson unless agreed otherwise. Dust samples will be collected from mattress and carpets in bedroom and living room.

4.5. SPECIFIC CLINICAL METHODS

4.5.1. Questionnaires

- ISAAC plus supplementary disease questionnaires: to assess asthma presence, morbidity, medication requirements and presence of other allergic disease.
- Environmental questionnaires: to evaluate exposures to allergens, irritants and frequency of respiratory infections.

4.5.2. Physical Examination

Physical examination will include assessment of vital signs, a general examination and chest auscultation. Height and weight will be recorded.

4.5.3. Skin Prick Test

Skin prick testing will be performed by experienced nurses using standard technique and protocol. Antihistamines will be withheld (if safe to do so) for 72 hours prior to the procedure. A panel of 9 common allergens will be tested comprising house dust mite (*Dermatophagoides pteronyssinus* and *farinae*, grass pollen mix, tree pollen mix, cat and dog epithelia, *Alternaria alternata*, *Cladosporium herbarum*, *Aspergillus* plus histamine and physiological saline to act as positive and negative controls, respectively). Allergen skin test reaction with a mean wheal diameter of at least 3 mm greater than the negative control will be regarded as positive and the subject defined as atopic.

4.5.4. Spirometry

Spirometry will follow American Thoracic Society guidelines to ensure spirometry validity and reproducibility. As recommended, the highest of three FEV₁ measurements within 5% of each other will be used. To perform this test, the subject will be required to be free from respiratory infection for 14 days, not taken short-acting beta-agonist medication for 6 hours, long-acting beta-2 agonists for 12 hours and long-acting muscarinic antagonists for 24 hours (if safe to do so). They will also be required to abstain from caffeine intake for at least 4 hours. We will record forced expiratory volume in one second (FEV₁), forced vital capacity (FVC), mid expiratory flow (MEF), peak expiratory flow (PEF), percent predicted for age, height, sex and ethnic origin and forced expiratory ratio (FEV₁/FVC) will be calculated for the above data.

4.5.5. Bronchial Hyperresponsiveness

Bronchial challenge will be performed using methacholine as the stimulant.¹³ Standard methodology for bronchial challenge will be undertaken consistent with that performed in previous studies at this Centre. Methacholine will be prepared according to a pre-specified protocol using a checklist following a specific Standardised Operating Procedure consistent with ERS technical standards.¹⁴

For the actual bronchial challenge, a safety checklist will be completed before each test. The test will then be conducted according to a designated protocol following a specific Standardised Operating Procedure. Salbutamol 600mcg will be prescribed on a trust drug chart for all participants for administration after the bronchial challenge test. The test will be carried out by a doctor or a registered trained nurse (with the additional presence of a doctor in the building).

A dosimeter system will be used (eg Koko dosimeter; PDS Instrumentation, with compressed air source at 8 l/minute and nebuliser output 0.8 l/minute). Initial inhalation of 0.9% Saline is followed 1 minute later by spirometry recording to obtain a baseline value. Baseline FEV₁ is required to be greater than 70% predicted to proceed with the test. Subsequently, incremental methacholine doses from 1mg to 32mg will be administered. The dose causing a 20% fall in FEV₁ from the post-saline value is interpolated and expressed as PD₂₀ FEV₁. To perform spirometry or bronchial challenge, subjects will be required to be free from respiratory infection for 14 days, not be taking oral steroids, not taken beta₂ agonist for 6 hours and have abstained from caffeine intake for at least 4 hours. A positive test is defined by PD₂₀ < 2µg. A continuous dose-response slope (DRS) measure of BHR will also be estimated by least-square regression of percentage change in FEV₁ upon cumulative methacholine dose for each subject. The DRS obtained will be transformed to satisfy normality and homoscedasticity. Results will be communicated to the participants' general practitioner (GP) by written letter.

To perform this test, subjects will be required to be free from respiratory infection for 14 days, not taking oral steroids, not taken short acting β₂ agonist for 6 hours, and long acting β₂ agonist for 12 hours, and abstained from caffeine intake for at least 4 hours.

4.5.6. Fractional Exhaled Nitric Oxide (FeNO) measurements:

Measurement of FeNO will be performed in all patients using standardised methodology. We will do real-time measurements during each subject's visits to the Centre.

4.6. STUDY DURATION

- Each participant is expected to give approximately 17 hours of their time (plus travelling time) to the study, which includes Centre and Home visits. It will be the aim to complete all study appointments in as short a timeframe as possible.
- Follow-up of the whole study sample is expected to last for 18 months. If during the study it becomes apparent that additional time will be required an amendment to the protocol will be submitted to the REC.

5. DATA MANAGEMENT

Research participants will be seen in the David Hide Asthma and Allergy Research Centre where all data will be gathered, processed and stored in a secure manner for statistical analysis. Data management will follow a similar pattern to that successfully used previously. An Access or SPSS database (Microsoft, USA), using study number only for identification will be set up. Current name and address will be entered into an Excel database. Study data will be stored in the Access database using the unique study number as the primary key, this data will be used to create separate analysis files in SPSS. The study number will link the subject's clinical information to the sample. Source data will be held securely on the Isle of Wight NHS local area network. Files used for analysis will not contain any personal identifiable information. Anonymised data may be transferred to University of Southampton, Faculty of Medicine for further analysis. At the end of the trial, anonymised data will be shared with Dyson Technology Ltd for their review. We will establish data sharing agreement with both organisations.

5.1. DATA PROTECTION AND STORAGE

Data will be collected and retained in accordance with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) 2018. All essential documents including source documents will be retained for a minimum period of 15 years following the end of the study. A 'DO NOT DESTROY' label stating the time after which the documents can be destroyed will be placed on the inner cover of the medical records of trial participants. All study documents will be stored securely at the study site i.e. David Hide Allergy and Asthma Centre at St Mary's Hospital, Isle of Wight.

5.2. STATISTICAL METHODS

All data will be entered or transferred into a data analysis programme (SPSS Inc., Chicago, USA). Data analysis will be blind. Continuous variables, which are generally normally distributed such as FEV₁ or PEF or PD₂₀ methacholine (after log conversion) will be compared using t-test. Other variables such as AQLQ and ACQ scores will be evaluated using Wilcoxon signed rank sum test. Number of occurrences (e.g. of exacerbations) will be compared using chi-squared test.

6. ETHICS

6.1. ADVERSE EVENTS

This research does not involve procedures with greater than minimal risks. The social and psychological risks of talking to interviewers when completing the questionnaires or the documentation sheets are minimal. Skin prick testing may cause minimal discomfort and occasionally large localised swelling but does not cause a systemic reaction. Lung function tests and exhaled nitric oxide test do not carry significant risk of any adverse effects. Bronchial challenge test can cause wheeze and chest discomfort but appropriate precautions are taken to avoid this and these symptoms can be treated with inhaled bronchodilators, which is routinely administered after the test. Very occasionally nebulised bronchodilators may be required to treat more than mild wheezing and asthma symptoms that may have been provoked. Rarely asthmatic patients can get a severe episode of asthma following the test and hence the test is always performed in the presence of a medically qualified and trained person, and facilities for immediate treatment of bronchospasm are at hand. The clinical team is experienced in the performance of these procedures and the vast majority of participants have performed these procedures safely in other studies being carried out at the Centre. The Centre also provides clinical care for asthma and allergy patients and many of these procedures are routinely used. The overall risk is similar to that of routine clinical care.

6.2. SAFEGUARDING

All members of the research team are trained in Safeguarding at a level appropriate to their role. The Isle of Wight NHS Trust policy on safeguarding will be followed in the event that a safeguarding issue arises.

A copy of the policy and procedures can be found on the Isle of Wight NHS Trust Intranet.

7. FINANCE AND INSURANCE

The study will be funded by Dyson Technology Ltd. as a block grant to cover all trial expenses. A detailed budget will be provided and approved by Dyson Technology Ltd. Insurance will be provided by the NHS Indemnity Scheme.

Participants will be reimbursed for their travel and parking expenses.

8. TRIAL MANAGEMENT AND OVERSIGHT ARRANGEMENTS

8.1. PROJECT MANAGEMENT GROUP

The trial will be coordinated by a Project Management Group consisting of the Chief Investigator (Professor Syed Hasan Arshad), Co- Investigator (Dr Ramesh Kurukulaaratchy), Research Fellow (to be appointed), Senior Research Nurse (Mrs Frances Mitchell), and Project Co-ordinator (Mr Stephen Potter). The group will meet once a month and additionally, as required by the needs of the trial. The meeting will be chaired by the Chief Investigator (or in his absence Co-Investigator). Research Fellow and/or Senior Research Nurse will present study progress including recruitment and assessments updates. Any issues will be discussed and resolved, including adverse effect, incidents of protocol deviation and violations, reports to the R&D and ethics committee and need for protocol amendments.

8.2. TRIAL MANAGEMENT

Research Fellow, Senior Research Nurse and Clinical Trial Assistant will be responsible for carrying out the study, which will be overseen by the Co-Investigator. Project Coordinator will be responsible for checking the CRFs for completeness, plausibility and consistency. The team will be accountable to the Chief Investigator, who is ultimately responsible for the conduct of the study according to the protocol. Any queries will be resolved by the Investigators or delegated member of the trial team. A Delegation Log will be prepared, detailing the responsibilities of each member of staff working on the trial.

8.3. INSPECTION OF RECORDS

Investigators and institutions involved in the study will permit trial related monitoring, audits, REC review, and regulatory inspection(s). In the event of an audit, the Chief Investigator agrees to allow the Sponsor, representatives of the Sponsor or regulatory authorities direct access to all study records and source documentation.

8.4. STUDY MONITORING

The study will be monitored and audited in accordance with Isle of Wight NHS Trust R&D procedures. All trial related documents will be made available on request for monitoring and audit by the relevant R&D and REC.

9. GOOD CLINICAL PRACTICE

The study will be performed subject to Research Ethics Committee (REC) approval, including any provisions of Site Specific Assessment (SSA), and local Research and Development (R&D) approval. The trial will be run according to the protocol approved by the Ethics Committee. Any amendments to the protocol will first be submitted for approval by the Ethics Committee before implementation. The study will be registered with ClinicalTrials.gov

9.1. ETHICAL CONDUCT OF THE STUDY

The study will be conducted in accordance with the principles of the Good Clinical Practice (GCP). A favorable ethical opinion will be obtained from the appropriate REC and local NHS R&D approval will be obtained prior to commencement of the study.

9.2. REGULATORY COMPLIANCE OF THE STUDY

The study will not commence until REC and local R&D approval is obtained.

9.3. INVESTIGATOR RESPONSIBILITIES

The Chief Investigator is responsible for the overall conduct of the study at the site and compliance with the protocol and any protocol amendments. Responsibilities may be delegated to an appropriate member of study site staff. Delegated tasks must be documented on a Delegation Log and signed by all those named on the list.

9.4. INFORMED CONSENT

- The Chief Investigator is responsible for ensuring informed consent is obtained before any protocol specific procedures are carried out. The decision of a participant to participate in clinical research is voluntary and should be based on a clear understanding of what is involved.
- The participant must receive adequate oral and written information – appropriate Participant Information and Informed Consent Forms will be provided. The oral explanation to the participant should be performed by the Investigators or designated person, and must cover all the elements specified in the Participant Information Sheet/Informed Consent.
- The participant must be given every opportunity to clarify any points they do not understand and, if necessary, ask for more information. The participant must be given sufficient time to consider the information provided. It should be emphasised that the participants may withdraw their consent to participate at any time without loss of benefits to which they otherwise would be entitled.
- The participant should be informed and agree to their medical records being inspected by regulatory authorities but understand that their name will not be disclosed outside the hospital.
- The participant should be informed and agree that Dyson Technologies will have access to the anonymised data of the trial, although no identifiable information will be disclosed to anyone outside the study team.
- The Chief Investigator or delegated member of the trial team and the participant should sign and date the Informed Consent Form(s) to confirm that consent has been obtained. The participant should receive a copy of this document and copies should be filed in the medical notes and Investigator Site File (ISF).

9.5. Study Site Staff

The Chief Investigator must be familiar with the protocol and the study requirements. It is the Chief Investigator's responsibility to ensure that all staff assisting with the study are adequately informed about and trained in the protocol and their trial related duties.

9.6. Data Recording

The Chief Investigator is responsible for the quality of the data recorded in the CRF.

9.7. Investigator Documentation

Prior to beginning the study, each Investigator will be asked to provide particular essential documents to the Sponsor, including but not limited to:

- An original signed Investigator's Declaration
- Curriculum vitae (CV) signed and dated by the Investigators and each study team members indicating that it is accurate and current.
- The Chief Investigator, with the agreement of the Sponsor, will ensure all other documents required for compliance with the principles of GCP are retained in a Trial Master File and that appropriate documentation is available in local ISFs.

9.8. GCP Training

All study staff must hold evidence of appropriate GCP training or undergo GCP training. This should be updated every two years throughout the trial.

9.9. Confidentiality

All evaluation forms, reports, and other records must be identified in a manner designed to maintain participant confidentiality. All records must be kept in a secure storage area with limited access. Clinical information will not be released without the written permission of the participant, except as necessary for monitoring and auditing by the Sponsor, its designee, or the REC or as required by law. The Investigators and study site staff involved with this study may not disclose or use for any purpose other than performance of the study, any data, record, or other unpublished, confidential information disclosed to those individuals for the purpose of the study. Prior written agreement from the Sponsor or its designee must be obtained for the disclosure of any said confidential information to other parties.

9.10. Data Protection

- All Investigators and study site staff involved with this study must comply with the requirements of the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) 2018 with regard to the collection, storage, processing and disclosure of personal information and will uphold the Act's core principles. Access to collated participant data will be restricted to those clinicians treating the participants.
- Computers used to collate the data will have limited access measures via user names and passwords.
- Published results or results shared with Dyson Technology Limited or any third parties will not contain any personal data that could allow identification of individual participants.

10. STUDY CONDUCT RESPONSIBILITIES

10.1. PROTOCOL AMENDMENTS

The trial will be run according to the protocol approved by the Ethics Committee. Any changes in research activity, except those necessary to remove an apparent, immediate hazard to the participant, must be reviewed and approved by the Chief Investigator. Amendments to the protocol must be submitted in writing to the appropriate REC and local R&D for approval prior to participants being enrolled into an amended protocol.

10.2. PROTOCOL VIOLATIONS AND DEVIATIONS

The study team will report any protocol violation and deviation to the chief investigator, who will ensure that RE and R&D are informed, if appropriate. The study team should not implement any deviation from the protocol without agreement from the Chief Investigator and appropriate REC and R&D approval except where necessary to eliminate an immediate hazard to trial participants.

In the event that study team needs to deviate from the protocol, the nature of and reasons for the deviation should be recorded in the CRF. If this necessitates a subsequent protocol amendment, this should be submitted to the REC and local R&D for review and approval, if appropriate. All protocol deviations and violation will be compiled and considered at the time of data analysis by Investigators and shared with the Category Development Manager (or equivalent) at Dyson Technology Limited.

10.3. REVIEW OF ADVERSE EFFECTS

If an adverse effect is reported at one of the regular contacts (Centre visit, home visit and telephone interview), or during the study procedures, all details will be recorded in the CRF and reported to the Investigators if needed. Appropriate actions will be taken to eliminate or minimize the risk to the participant. Additionally, participants will be provided with an emergency 24 hour telephone number to report any adverse effect. Any SAEs and AEs will be tabulated. The Project Management Group will review safety data on an ongoing basis but specifically at their monthly meeting, all recorded adverse effects will be reviewed. The Project Management Group will be responsible for classifying, documenting, determining causality and reporting.

Adverse events (serious versus non-serious)

Adverse events: An adverse event (AE) can be any unfavourable and unintended sign (including an abnormal laboratory finding), symptom, or disease temporally associated with the intervention or procedure carried out as part of the research study. Adverse events will be recorded in accordance with the GCP recommendations.

Serious Adverse Event (SAE): Defined as any untoward medical occurrence that at any dose:

- results in death,
- is life-threatening,
- requires inpatient hospitalization or prolongation of existing hospitalization,
- results in persistent or significant disability/incapacity,
- is a congenital anomaly/birth defect

The reporting and follow-up of serious and non-serious adverse reaction will follow standards recommendation of the ICH, GCP guidelines.

www.emea.europa.eu/pdfs/human/ich/013595en.pdf

10.4. PROCEDURES FOR CODE BREAKING

Study codes will be kept locked and only the Chief Investigator and Project Coordinator will have access to these. If there is concern regarding the health of the participant, the Project Coordinator, in consultation with Chief Investigator, will make the decision to break the code.

10.5. STUDY RECORD RETENTION

All study documentation will be kept for at least 15 years.

10.6. END OF STUDY

- The end of study is defined as the last participant's last visit.
- Chief Investigators, in consultation with the Project Management Group, has the right to terminate the study for clinical or administrative reasons.
- The end of the study will be reported to the REC within 90 days, or 15 days if the study is terminated prematurely. The study team and Investigators will inform participants and ensure that the appropriate follow up is arranged for all involved.
- A summary report of the study will be provided to the REC within 1 year of the end of the study.

11. REPORTING, PUBLICATIONS AND NOTIFICATION OF RESULTS

11.1. AUTHORSHIP POLICY

Chief Investigator will be the custodian of the data arising from this study and the Sponsor should be the owner of the data. On completion of the study, the study data will be analysed and tabulated, and a clinical study report will be prepared.

11.2. PUBLICATION

- The clinical study report and its results will be used for publication and presentation at scientific meetings. Investigators have the right to publish orally or in writing the results of the study.
- Summaries of results will also be made available to Investigators for dissemination within their clinics (where appropriate and according to their discretion). The results of the study will be published in peer reviewed scientific journals and will be presented at national and international conferences. Findings will also be shared in plain English with the participants in our newsletters and via The David Hide Asthma and Allergy Research Centre website.

12. REFERENCES

1. Arshad SH, Hamilton RG, Adkinson NF, Jr. Repeated aerosol exposure to small doses of allergen. A model for chronic allergic asthma. *American journal of respiratory and critical care medicine* 1998;157:1900-6.
2. Habre R, Moshier E, Castro W, et al. The effects of PM_{2.5} and its components from indoor and outdoor sources on cough and wheeze symptoms in asthmatic children. *Journal Of Exposure Science And Environmental Epidemiology* 2014;24:380.
3. Polosa R. The interaction between particulate air pollution and allergens in enhancing allergic and airway responses. *Current allergy and asthma reports* 2001;1:102-7.
4. Gold DR, Adamkiewicz G, Arshad SH, et al. NIAID, NIEHS, NHLBI, and MCAN Workshop Report: The indoor environment and childhood asthma-implications for home environmental intervention in asthma prevention and management. *The Journal of allergy and clinical immunology* 2017;140:933-49.
5. Eldridge MW, Peden DB. Allergen provocation augments endotoxin-induced nasal inflammation in subjects with atopic asthma. *Journal of Allergy and Clinical Immunology* 2000;105:475-81.
6. Matsui EC, Hansel NN, Aloe C, et al. Indoor pollutant exposures modify the effect of airborne endotoxin on asthma in urban children. *American journal of respiratory and critical care medicine* 2013;188:1210-5.
7. Paulin LM, Diette GB, Scott M, et al. Home interventions are effective at decreasing indoor nitrogen dioxide concentrations. *Indoor air* 2014;24:416-24.
8. Butz AM, Matsui EC, Breysse P, et al. A randomized trial of air cleaners and a health coach to improve indoor air quality for inner-city children with asthma and secondhand smoke exposure. *Archives of pediatrics & adolescent medicine* 2011;165:741-8.
9. Lanphear BP, Hornung RW, Khoury J, Yolton K, Lierl M, Kalkbrenner A. Effects of HEPA air cleaners on unscheduled asthma visits and asthma symptoms for children exposed to secondhand tobacco smoke. *Pediatrics* 2011;127:93-101.
10. Francis H, Fletcher G, Anthony C, et al. Clinical effects of air filters in homes of asthmatic adults sensitized and exposed to pet allergens. *Clinical and experimental allergy : journal of the British Society for Allergy and Clinical Immunology* 2003;33:101-5.
11. Boyle RJ, Pedroletti C, Wickman M, et al. Nocturnal temperature controlled laminar airflow for treating atopic asthma: a randomised controlled trial. *Thorax* 2012;67:215-21.
12. Brazier P, Schauer U, Hamelmann E, Holmes S, Pritchard C, Warner JO. Economic analysis of temperature-controlled laminar airflow (TLA) for the treatment of patients with severe persistent allergic asthma. *BMJ open respiratory research* 2016;3:e000117.
13. Anderson SD, Brannan J, Spring J, et al. A new method for bronchial-provocation testing in asthmatic subjects using a dry powder of mannitol. *American journal of respiratory and critical care medicine* 1997;156:758-65.

14. Coates AL, Wanger J, Cockcroft DW, et al. ERS technical standard on bronchial challenge testing: general considerations and performance of methacholine challenge tests. The European respiratory journal 2017;49.

STUDY SCHEDULE

Months	Work Description
July 2018 – September 2018	Finalise protocol, Ethics application, R&D approvals, data base, study tools and CRF developments
September 2018 – October 2018	Recruitment, pre-trial assessments,
October 2018 - April 2019	Clinical assessments and data entry
May 2019 – July 2019	Data analysis, preparation of manuscripts (based on RCT part of the study)
October 2019 – Dec 2019	Data analysis, preparation of manuscripts (based on open label part of the study)
Dec 2019	End of study Report

Table : Dyson asthma trial schedule

Procedures	Screening Centre visit 1 -2--4 weeks	Home visit 1 0 week	Telephone contact 6-7 weeks	Centre Visit 2 12-13 weeks	Telephone contact 18-19 weeks	Centre Visit 3 (plus home visit 2) 24-26 week	Telephone contact 36-38 weeks	Visit 4 (plus home visit 3) 50-54 weeks
	RANDOMISED CONTROLLED TRIAL						OPEN LABEL STUDY	
PIS explanation/ consent	X	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Medical/allergic history questionnaires	X	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Asthma control questionnaire	X	-	X	X	X	X	X	X
Asthma quality of life questionnaire (self-administered)	X	-	X	X	X	X	X	X
Rhinitis quality of life questionnaire (self-administered)	X	-	X	X	X	X	X	X
Asthma diary (medication and exacerbation, PFR) completed by patient for 2 weeks	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Physical examination (vital signs, chest auscultation)	X	-	-	X	-	-	-	X
Skin prick test	X	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Spirometry	X	-	-	X	-	X	-	X
Bronchial challenge (Methacholine)	X	-	-	X	-	X	-	X
Exhaled nitric oxide	X	-	-	X	-	X	-	X
Dust sample collection	-	X	-	-	-	X	-	X
Blood sample	X	-	-	-	-	X	-	X
Installation of air purifiers	-	X	-	-	-	X	-	-
Return of air purifiers	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	X
Letter to GP	X	-	-	-	-	-	-	-